

The Duration Of Postoperative Analgesia Using Low Dose Intravenous Ketamine In Patients Undergoing Elective Cesarean Section With Spinal Anesthesia A Randomized Controlled Trial

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Abstract

Introduction: Spinal anaesthesia has been the preferred choice for caesarean section now a days. Suitable analgesia after caesarean section helps mothers to be more comfortable and increases their ability to take better care of their infants. Postoperative pain has numerous side effects, including atelectasis, thrombosis, myocardial ischemia, cardiac arrhythmias, electrolyte imbalance, ileus, and urinary retention. This study is designed to estimate the duration of postoperative analgesia using low dose intravenous ketamine as used in the parent study.

Objective

To compare the mean duration of postoperative analgesia between low dose intravenous ketamine with intrathecal Bupivacaine and intrathecal Bupivacaine alone in patients undergoing elective caesarean section under spinal anaesthesia.

- *Setting :This study was conducted at Department of Anaesthesiology, Surgical Intensive Care Unit and Pain Management Clinic, Dow University of Health Sciences, Dr. Ruth K. M. Pfau Civil Hospital Karachi, Pakistan.*

- *Duration: 6 months (from 24th February 2017 to 23rd August 2017).*

- *Design: Randomized Controlled Trial,*

Subject and Methods

Patients were presented in elective Obstetric operation theatre of Dr. Ruth K. M. Pfau Civil Hospital Karachi. A total of 60 women undergoing elective caesarean section were randomly allocated into two groups. Thirty were treated with bupivacaine-ketamine (group BK) and 30 were treated with bupivacaine alone (group B). Duration of postoperative analgesia was assessed every 30 minutes using VAS numeric pain scale by a single observer were blinding to group allocation. The end point of the study was when VAS score ≥ 4 or when patients requested for analgesia postoperatively.

Results

The average age and weight of the patients was 27.50 ± 4.80 years and 59.37 ± 6.83 kg respectively in group BK, and 25.93 ± 5.33 years and 63.47 ± 5.74 kg in group B as tabulated in table 1. Mean duration of analgesia was significantly high in group BK as compare to group B [3.85 ± 0.98 h vs. 1.40 ± 0.62 h; $p=0.0005$].

Conclusion

Intravenous low-dose ketamine during spinal anaesthesia for elective caesarean section provides more effective and long lasting pain relief than control group.

Introduction

Spinal anaesthesia has been the preferred choice for caesarean section now a days. Suitable analgesia after caesarean section helps mothers to be more comfortable and increases their mobility and ability to take better care of their infants[1]. Postoperative pain has numerous side effects, including (but not limited to) atelectasis, thrombosis, myocardial ischemia, cardiac arrhythmias, electrolyte imbalance, ileus and urinary retention. Multimodal analgesic techniques appear most effective [2]. Low dose ketamine has been considered as good substitute for opioids for controlling postoperative pain[3].

In a study conducted on 60 women undergoing caesarean delivery under spinal anaesthesia concluded that ketamine group had significant pain relief properties in comparison with control group in first hour after

caesarean section (0.78 ± 1.09 vs. 1.72 ± 1.22 , VAS score, $p=0.00$) [1]. Intrathecal combination of low-dose ketamine, midazolam and low-dose bupivacaine improves hemodynamics and postoperative analgesia [4]. Another study reveals that intravenous low-dose ketamine combined with intrathecal bupivacaine (197min) for caesarean section provides longer postoperative analgesia and lower postoperative analgesic consumption than bupivacaine alone (144min) suggesting a pre-emptive effect [5]. Significantly less fentanyl was used in the ketamine groups 2h after surgery ($p=0.033$) when used in post-caesarean delivery analgesia after spinal anaesthesia [6]. There was no difference regarding early and late postoperative pain and morphine consumption with ketamine at doses of 0.25, 0.5 and 1 mg/kg in women undergoing caesarean delivery under general anaesthesia [7]. The mean time of first postoperative analgesic administration was significantly longer in Group BK (209 ± 14.7 min) than in Group B (164 ± 14.1 min) ($p < 0.001$). Pain scores were significantly lower in group BK than in group B for 120 min after surgery ($p=0.022$) [8].

Rational

Since spinal anaesthesia is preferred choice of caesarean delivery but postoperative pain remains problematic. Many drugs have been used in this context but intravenous ketamine have not been studied as such. So the rational of my study is to estimate the duration of postoperative analgesia using low-dose intravenous ketamine as used in the present study.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

Setting: This study was conducted at Department of Anaesthesiology, Surgical Intensive Care Unit and Pain Management Clinic, Dow University of Health Sciences, Dr. Ruth K. M. Pfau Civil Hospital Karachi, Pakistan.

Duration of Study: 6 months (from 24th February 2017 to 23 August 2017).

Sample Size:

Mean \pm SD = 2.76 ± 1.28 [3]

Mean \pm SD = 1.36 ± 1.28 [3]

Confidence interval = 95%

Power = 80%

N = sample size = 8 number of patients in each group

But we will take minimum 30 patients in each groups.

Sample Selection:

Inclusion Criteria

- American Society of Anaesthesiologist (ASA) physical status II
- Females of child bearing age 18-40 years
- Undergoing elective caesarean delivery

Exclusion Criteria

- Lack of consent by patients
- History of chronic opioid use
- History of hypersensitivity to local anaesthetic agent.
- Contraindications to spinal anaesthesia.

Study Design: Randomized controlled trial, Double blinded study

Sampling Techniques: Non-probability, consecutive sampling

DATA COLLECTION PROCEDURE:

After approval from College of Physicians and Surgeons of Pakistan and ethical committee of Dow University of health sciences meeting inclusion criteria was included in the study. Informed and written consent was taken from patients. Patients were randomly allocated by computer generated random number in two groups.

Group BK (Bupivacaine-Ketamine): was received intravenous midazolam 1mg and intravenous ketamine 0.25mg/kg after spinal anaesthesia with hyperbaric bupivacaine 0.5% (12mg)

Group B (Bupivacaine alone) was received intravenous midazolam 1mg after spinal anaesthesia with hyperbaric bupivacaine 0.5% (12mg).

Standard monitors were applied to every patient including NIBP, pulse oximeter & ECG. Patients were preloaded with 10ml/kg intravenous crystalloid. Spinal anaesthesia to all patients was given by single experienced anaesthetist with 25G Quincke needle in sitting position with hyperbaric bupivacaine 0.5% 12mg, patients were placed in supine position with wedge under right hip, level of block was established. 1mg midazolam and 0.25mg/kg ketamine was given intravenously according to groups allocation. Duration of postoperative analgesia was assessed every 30 minutes using VAS numeric pain scale by a single observer who was blinded to group allocation. The end point of the study was when VAS score ≥ 4 or when patients were requested for analgesia postoperatively.

DATA ANALYSIS PROCEDURE:

Data entry and statistical analysis was done using statistical packages of social science 20. Mean and SD was computed for quantitative variables like age, weight and duration of postoperative analgesia. T test was applied

to compare the duration of post-operative analgesia between two groups. P-Value <0.05 was considered significant.

Stratification was done to control effect modifiers like age and weight to observe an outcome. Post stratification t test was applied. P-Value <0.05 was considered significant.

RESULTS

A total of 60 women undergoing elective caesarean section were randomly allocated into two groups. Thirty were treated with bupivacaine-ketamine (group BK) and 30 were treated with bupivacaine alone (group B). The average age and weight of the patients was 27.50±4.80 years and 59.37±6.83 kg respectively in group BK, 25.93±5.33 years and 63.47±5.74 kg respectively in group B as tabulated in table 1.

Comparison of mean duration of postoperative analgesia between groups is shown in figure 1. Mean duration of analgesia was significantly high in group BK as compare to group B [3.85±0.98h vs. 1.40±0.62 h; p=0.0005]. Stratification analysis was performed and observed that mean duration of analgesia was significantly high in group BK as compare to group B for given age groups (table 2) and weight groups (table 3) .

TABLE 1
DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS OF AGE AND WEIGHT
ACCORDING TO GROUPS

Variables	GROUP BK n=30		GROUP B n=30		Total n=60	
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation
Age (Years)	27.50	4.80	25.93	5.33	26.72	5.09
Weight (kg)	59.37	6.83	63.47	5.74	61.42	6.58

FIGURE 1
COMPARISON OF DURATION OF POSTOPERATIVE ANALGESIA (IN HOURS) BETWEEN
GROUPS
n=60

TABLE 2
COMPARISON OF DURATION OF POSTOPERATIVE ANALGESIA BETWEEN GROUPS BY AGE
GROUPS
n=60

Age Groups (Years)	GROUP BK			GROUP B			P-Value
	n	Mean duration of postoperative analgesia	Std. Deviation	n	Mean duration of postoperative analgesia	Std. Deviation	
<=25	13	3.62	1.04	17	1.41	0.71	0.0005
26 to 30	11	4.23	0.87	6	1.33	0.51	0.0005
>30	6	3.67	0.98	7	1.43	0.53	0.0005

TABLE 3
COMPARISON OF DURATION OF POSTOPERATIVE ANALGESIA BETWEEN GROUPS BY
WEIGHT
n=60

Weight	GROUP BK			GROUP B			P-Value
	n	Mean duration of postoperative analgesia	Std. Deviation	n	Mean duration of postoperative analgesia	Std. Deviation	
≤60 kg	20	3.65	1.12	16	1.31	0.47	0.0005
>60kg	10	4.25	0.43	14	1.50	0.76	0.0005

DISCUSSION

Suitable analgesia after caesarean section helps mothers to be more comforted

and increases their mobility in order to prevent deep vein thrombosis and ability to take better care of their infants [9]. Different analgesic drugs had been utilized to block multiple pain pathways and reduce side effects of sedative drugs. Opioids are transferred into the milk and might impact neonates. It seemed that maternal intake of these drugs such as opioids had to be declined [10,11]. Ketamine with sub anaesthetic doses has analgesic effects which had been used for chronic pain relief. Several clinical trials have reported that ketamine can be administered during anaesthesia to reduce opioids needs for postoperative pain relief. Cochrane review at 2006 reported that “Ketamine in sub-anaesthetic doses is effective in reducing analgesic requirements in the first 24 hours after surgery” [12]. Ketamine, also decreases postoperative analgesic consumption due to prevention from opioids tolerance [13]. This impact was also seen in using sub-anaesthetic dosage of ketamine (0.15 mg/kg) during spinal anaesthesia for caesarean section [14,15].

In this study the average age of the patients was 27.50±4.80 years in group BK and 25.93±5.33 years in group B. The average weight of the patients was 59.37± 6.83 kg in group BK and 63.47±5.74 kg in group B. In Behdad et al study [1] mean age and weight in participated women were 28.34 ± 5.15 years and 72.06 ± 15.03 kilogram respectively.

In present study mean duration of analgesia was significantly high in group BK as compare to group B [3.85±0.98h vs. 1.40±0.62 h; p=0.0005]. Similar result was also reported in a study, they conducted on 160 women undergoing caesarean delivery under spinal anaesthesia concluded that using low dose intravenous ketamine (0.25mg/kg) significantly prolonged duration of analgesia as compared with control group (2.76 ± 1.28 vs. 1.36 ± 0.48, p<0.001) [3]. Role of ketamine in reducing need for opium analgesia was reported in several studies [16,17]. Researchers used ketamine as intravenous patients control analgesia (IVPCA) [18,19] IV continues [20,21]. IV continues with epidural opium [22,23], IV ketamine with epidural opium [23,24], ketamine epidural [25,26] and IM, IV ketamine in paediatric analgesia for tonsillectomy [27,28]. In gynaecology surgery, there were some studies which had been used ketamine in sub anaesthetic dosage. Sen et al. reported that women who received ketamine (0.15 mg/kg) during spinal anaesthesia for CS operation had declined diclofenac

requirement in the first day postoperatively [5]. Kwol et al. in laparoscopic gynaecology surgery reported that reduced requirement of paracetamol in the first week postoperatively in women who received ketamine (0.15 mg/kg) [29]. Against above studies, Dahl et al. reported no opioids-sparing effects with single doses of ketamine (0.4 mg/kg) in women who underwent abdominal hysterectomy [30]. In non-gynaecology operation, single doses of ketamine (0.05-0.15 mg/kg) reduced opioids consumption following orthopaedic surgery with sustained effects up to three days after arthroscopy [31]. Clinical trials which used low-dose ketamine had been suggested a number of mechanisms for the analgesic effects. These include supraspinal effects, prevention of acute opioid tolerance and suppression of central sensitization, a phenomenon by which dorsal root neurons increase their spontaneous discharge rate, responsiveness and enlarge their receptive field in response to repeated painful stimulus. Caesarean delivery can lead to chronic pain in 6–8% of patients [32,33]. After seeing our results, the studies further using ketamine in managing post operative pain after caesarean section are guaranteed.

CONCLUSION

In present study mean duration of analgesia was significantly high in ketamine group BK as compared to control group B. It is recommended that due to significant postoperative pain relief without considerable side effects, Intravenous low-dose ketamine during spinal anaesthesia for elective Caesarean section provides more effective and long lasting pain relief than control group.

REFERENCES

- Behdad S, Hajiesmaeili MR, Abbasi HR, Ayatollahi V, Khadiv Z, Sedaghat A. Analgesic Effects of Intravenous Ketamine during Spinal Anaesthesia in Pregnant Women Undergone Caesarean Section; A Randomized Clinical Trial. *Anesth Pain Med.* 2013 Sep;3(2):230-3
- Kelly DJ, Ahmad M, Brull SJ. Preemptive analgesia I: physiological pathways and pharmacological modalities. *Can J Anaesth.* 2001 Nov;48(10):1000-10
- Rahmanian M, Leysi M, Hemmati AA, Mirmohammadkhani M. The effect of low-dose intravenous ketamine on postoperative pain following caesarean section with spinal anaesthesia: a randomized clinical trial. *Oman Med J.* 2015 Jan;30(1):11-6.
- Basuni AS. Addition of low-dose ketamine to midazolam and low-dose bupivacaine improves hemodynamics and postoperative analgesia during spinal anesthesia for cesarean section. *J AnaesthesiolClinPharmacol.* 2016 Jan-Mar;32(1):44-8
- Sen S, Ozmert G, Aydin ON, Baran N, Caliskan E. The persisting analgesic effect of low-dose intravenous ketamine after spinal anaesthesia for caesarean section. *Eur J Anaesthesiol.* 2005 Jul;22(7):518-23.
- SeungYeup Han, HeeCheolJin, Woo Dae Yang, JoonHo Lee, Seong Hwan Cho, Won SeokChae, et al. The Effect of Low-dose Ketamine on Post-caesarean Delivery Analgesia after Spinal Anaesthesia. *Korean J Pain.* 2013; 26(3): 270–276.
- Bilgen S, Köner O, Türe H, Menda F, Fiçicioğlu C, Aykaç B. Effect of three different doses of ketamine prior to general anaesthesia on postoperative pain following Caesarean delivery: a prospective randomized study. *Minerva Anesthesiol.* 2012 Apr;78(4):442-9
- Menkiti ID1, Desalu I, Kushimo OT. Low-dose intravenous ketamine improves postoperative analgesia after caesarean delivery with spinal bupivacaine in African parturients. *Int J ObstetAnesth.* 2012 Jul;21(3):217-21
- Yost NP, Bloom SL, Sibley MK, Lo JY, McIntire DD, Leveno KJ. A hospital sponsored quality improvement study of pain management after caesarean delivery. *Am J Obstet Gynecol.* 2004;190(5):1341-6.
- Bar-Oz B, Bulkowstein M, Benyamini L, Greenberg R, Soriano I, Zimmerman D, et al. Use of antibiotic and analgesic drugs during lactation. *Drug Saf.* 2003;26(13):925-35.
- Wittels B, Glosten B, Faure EA, Moawad AH, Ismail M, Hibbard J, et al. Postcesarean analgesia with both epidural morphine and intravenous patient-controlled analgesia: neurobehavioral outcomes among nursing neonates. *AnesthAnalg.* 1997;85(3):600-6.
- Bell RF, Dahl JB, Moore RA, Kalso E. Perioperative ketamine for acute postoperative pain. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 2006;(1):CD004603.
- Mao J, Price DD, Mayer DJ. Mechanisms of hyperalgesia and morphine tolerance: a current view of their possible interactions. *Pain.* 1995;62(3):259-74.
- Kashefi P. The benefits of intraoperative small-dose ketamine on postoperative pain after caesarean section. *Anesthesiology.* 2006;104:27.
- Sen S, Ozmert G, Aydin ON, Baran N, Caliskan E. The persisting analgesic effect of low-dose intravenous ketamine after spinal anaesthesia for caesarean section. *Eur J Anaesthesiol.* 2005;22(7):518- 23.
- Burstal R, Danjoux G, Hayes C, Lantry G. PCA ketamine and morphine after abdominal hysterectomy. *Anaesth Intensive Care.* 2001;29(3):246-51.

- Hercoc T, Gillham MJ, Sleight J, Jones SF. The addition of ketamine to patient controlled morphine analgesia does not improve quality of analgesia after total abdominal hysterectomy. *Acute Pain*. 1999;2(2):68-72.
- Murdoch CJ, Crooks BA, Miller CD. Effect of the addition of ketamine to morphine in patient-controlled analgesia. *Anaesthesia*. 2002;57(5):484-8.
- Guillou N, Tanguy M, Seguin P, Branger B, Campion JP, Malledant Y. The effects of small-dose ketamine on morphine consumption in surgical intensive care unit patients after major abdominal surgery. *AnesthAnalg*. 2003;97(3):843-7.
- Heinke W, Grimm D. [Preemptive effects caused by co-analgesia with ketamine in gynaecological laparotomies?]. *AnaesthesiolReanim*. 1999;24(3):60-4.
- Jaksch W, Lang S, Reichhalter R, Raab G, Dann K, Fitzal S. Perioperative small-dose S(+)-ketamine has no incremental beneficial effects on postoperative pain when standard-practice opioid infusions are used. *AnesthAnalg*. 2002;94(4):981-6.
- De Kock M, Lavand'homme P, Waterloos H. 'Balanced analgesia' in the perioperative period: is there a place for ketamine? *Pain*. 2001;92(3):373-80.
- Kararmaz A, Kaya S, Karaman H, Turhanoglu S, Ozyilmaz MA. Intraoperative intravenous ketamine in combination with epidural analgesia: postoperative analgesia after renal surgery. *AnesthAnalg*. 2003;97(4):1092-6.
- Menigaux C, Fletcher D, Dupont X, Guignard B, Guirimand F, Chauvin M. The benefits of intraoperative small-dose ketamine on postoperative pain after anterior cruciate ligament repair. *AnesthAnalg*. 2000;90(1):129-35.
- Xie H, Wang X, Liu G, Wang G. Analgesic effects and pharmacokinetics of a low dose of ketamine preoperatively administered epidurally or intravenously. *Clin J Pain*. 2003;19(5):317-22
- Subramaniam B, Subramaniam K, Pawar DK, Sennaraj B. Preoperative epidural ketamine in combination with morphine does not have a clinically relevant intra- and postoperative opioid-sparing effect. *AnesthAnalg*. 2001;93(5):1321-6.
- Elhakim M, Khalafallah Z, El-Fattah HA, Farouk S, Khattab A. Ketamine reduces swallowing-evoked pain after paediatric tonsillectomy. *ActaAnaesthesiol Scand*. 2003;47(5):604-9.
- O'Flaherty JE, Lin CX. Does ketamine or magnesium affect post tonsillectomy pain in children? *PaediatrAnaesth*. 2003;13(5):413-21.
- Kwok RF, Lim J, Chan MT, Gin T, Chiu WK. Preoperative ketamine improves postoperative analgesia after gynecologic laparoscopic surgery. *AnesthAnalg*. 2004;98(4):1044-9.
- Dahl V, Ernoe PE, Steen T, Raeder JC, White PF. Does ketamine have preemptive effects in women undergoing abdominal hysterectomy procedures? *AnesthAnalg*. 2000;90(6):1419-22.
- Menigaux C, Guignard B, Fletcher D, Sessler DI, Dupont X, Chauvin M. Intraoperative small-dose ketamine enhances analgesia after outpatient knee arthroscopy. *AnesthAnalg*. 2001;93(3):606-12.
- Loos MJ, Scheltinga MR, Mulders LG, Roumen RM. The Pfannenstiel incision as a source of chronic pain. *Obstet Gynecol*. 2008;111(4):839-46.
- Nikolajsen L, Sorensen HC, Jensen TS, Kehlet H. Chronic pain following Caesarean section. *ActaAnaesthesiol Scand*. 2004;48(1):111-6.

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